

Beyond LLMs: Traditional Augmentation Dominates Fine-Grained Emotion Classification

Akrshita Sharma¹, Kushal Sharma¹, and Anamika Rangra²

¹ P.G. Student, Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering, Himachal Pradesh Technical University, Hamirpur, India

² Faculty, Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering, Himachal Pradesh Technical University, Hamirpur, India

Email: ¹akrshita2002@gmail.com, ¹kushalsharma98566@gmail.com, ²rangra.anamika@gmail.com

ORCID Id: ¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-1386-3644>, ¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-9870-2047>,

²<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3213-6493>

Corresponding Author*: Akrshita Sharma

ABSTRACT: Even the classification of fine-grained emotions in large label spaces is difficult because the classes are very imbalanced. This paper presents an empirical study assessing 12 data augmentation approaches to the problem of multi-label emotion classification on the GoEmotions dataset of 58,009 Reddit comments labelled across 27 emotion categories. We contrast the results of LLM-based (Mistral-7B, GPT-2, LLaMA-2), traditional NLP (backtranslation, T5 paraphrase), embedding-based (SimCSE, Hybrid), and resampling (SMOTE) augmentation on both DistilBERT-base and RoBERTa-base models. The F1 Macro of LLaMA-2 backtranslation is the highest at 0.540 on RoBERTa, surpassing the prior state-of-the-art of 0.494. A combined augmentation condition reports the best DistilBERT outcome (F1 Macro: 0.695), an improvement of +24.7% over baseline, demonstrating that augmentation diversity provides complementary signal. SMOTE underperforms the baseline, confirming its inability to operate on discrete text. BERTScore above 0.85 is validated as an effective pre-screening tool for augmentation quality. These results generalize insights on generative and hybrid augmentation through full intrinsic quality analysis and multi-seed stability evaluation, offering practical guidance for practitioners tackling imbalanced, fine-grained text classification tasks.

KEYWORDS: Data Augmentation, Emotion Classification, GoEmotions, DistilBERT, RoBERTa, LLaMA-2, BERTScore

1. Introduction

Text-based emotion recognition is a key issue in natural language processing and affective computing. The GoEmotions dataset released as open-source by Google Research [3] contains Reddit comments labeled with 27 emotion types and one neutral class, posing a significant challenge for automated systems.

Unlike earlier emotion datasets that covered at most six to eight categories, GoEmotions features highly similar but distinct emotions such as admiration versus approval, and grief versus sadness. This granularity significantly increases the classification difficulty.

A critical challenge is severe class imbalance: emotions such as grief, pride, and relief have very few labeled instances, making it difficult for models to learn these categories effectively. Data augmentation — generating synthetic training examples — is a natural solution, yet inserting meaning-preserving text examples is considerably harder than augmenting images. The closest prior work by Radlinski et al. [1] achieved F1 Macro 0.494 on DistilBERT using DeepL backtranslation. Our earlier study [20] indicated that combining generative, conventional, and hybrid augmentation yields synergistic gains. The present paper provides a complete systematic comparison of twelve augmentation strategies on two transformer architectures, with intrinsic quality analysis and multi-seed stability evaluation.

Three research questions guide this study: (i) Which augmentation method delivers the best performance on fine-grained multi-label emotion classification? (ii) Are intrinsic measures — BERTScore [14], SBERT cosine similarity [12], and TTR [19] — reliable predictors of downstream performance? (iii) Does augmentation method selection interact with transformer architecture (DistilBERT vs. RoBERTa)?

2. Methods and Methodology

A. Related Work — Data Augmentation for NLP

Wei and Zou [10] presented Easy Data Augmentation (EDA), a hybrid of synonym replacement, random insertion, swap, and deletion. Sennrich et al. [11] proposed NMT with backtranslation, modified by Xie et al. [16] for classification and applied to GoEmotions by Radlinski et al. [1]. Brown et al. [7] demonstrated GPT-3 few-shot data generation, influencing LLM-based augmentation; Dai et al. [23] followed with AugGPT. Gao et al. [5]

proposed SimCSE for contrastive embeddings. Feng et al. [22], Chai et al. [17], and Mumuni and Mumuni [25] provide comprehensive surveys. Wang et al. [18] studied LLM-augmented fine-grained emotion detection. Yang et al. [24] proposed dataset auditing with LLMs to improve label quality. Moller et al. [8] examined the parrot dilemma of label quality versus generation diversity. The authors' prior work has also explored hybrid deep-learning architectures in computer vision [26][27], suggesting cross-modal augmentation potential for future research.

B. Related Work — Transformer Models and Evaluation

Devlin et al. [15] proposed BERT; Liu et al. [13] enhanced it with RoBERTa through more robust pretraining. DistilBERT [9] achieves 97% of BERT performance with only 60% of the parameters. Zhang et al. [4] introduced the PAWS paraphrase dataset for fine-tuning T5. BERTScore [14] provides token-level evaluation of generation quality; Sentence-BERT [12] computes semantic similarity efficiently; Covington and McFall [19] proposed MATTR for lexical diversity. Parameter-efficient fine-tuning under data scarcity is addressed in [21].

C. Dataset

The GoEmotions dataset contains 58,009 Reddit comments labeled across 27 emotion categories plus neutral. We split the data 80%/20% using stratified random sampling with seed 42 to preserve class distributions. Table 1 lists the five most underrepresented emotion classes targeted for augmentation.

Table 1. Five Most Underrepresented Emotion Classes

Label Id	Emotion	Train Instances
12	Grief	96
19	Pride	142
23	Relief	182
21	Nervousness	208
16	Embarrassment	375

Note: Table 1 lists the five most underrepresented emotion classes targeted for augmentation, each with fewer than 400 training instances out of the full 58,009-sample corpus.

D. Augmentation Methods

Twelve augmentation conditions were evaluated. LLM-based methods include: Mistral-7B (few-shot rephrasing), GPT-2 (conditional text generation with an emotion prefix), T5 Paraphrase (a T5-base model fine-tuned on PAWS [4]), and LLaMA-2 in three configurations — zero-shot generation, few-shot paraphrase, and backtranslation (English → German → English). Embedding-based methods include SimCSE [5] (k-NN retrieval) and Hybrid SimCSE+Flan-T5 (retrieval followed by paraphrase). The resampling baseline is SMOTE [6] applied 3× in SBERT embedding space. A Combined condition merges all eleven approaches, contributing approximately 5,782 additional examples. All individual methods produced around 800 synthetic samples targeting the five minority classes.

E. Model Architecture and Training

Two transformer architectures were evaluated: DistilBERT-base-uncased (66M parameters) [9] and RoBERTa-base (125M parameters) [13], both trained on the 27-class multi-label classification task using sigmoid output activation and binary cross-entropy loss. Multi-seed evaluation (seeds 42, 21, 84) was performed for LLaMA-2 Backtranslation. Training hyperparameters are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Training Hyperparameters

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning Rate	2e-5
Batch Size	16
Epochs	3
Optimizer	AdamW
LR Scheduler	Cosine + Warmup

Warmup Ratio	0.1
Weight Decay	0.01
Max Seq. Length	128 tokens
Threshold	0.5 (sigmoid)

Note: Table 2 summarizes the fixed training configuration applied uniformly to both DistilBERT and RoBERTa across all augmentation conditions to ensure a fair comparison.

F. Evaluation Metrics

The primary metric is F1 Macro (unweighted mean per-class F1 across all 27 classes). Secondary metrics include subset accuracy, Precision Macro, and Recall Macro. Intrinsic quality indicators are: (i) TTR — per-text average type-token ratio [19]; (ii) SBERT cosine similarity [12]; and (iii) BERTScore F1 [14] using a quality threshold of 0.85.

Table 5. Intrinsic Augmentation Quality Metrics

Method	TTR	Cosine Sim.	BERTScore
Mistral-7B	0.9123	0.3412	0.8131
GPT-2	0.7330	0.1560	0.8209
T5 Paraphrase	0.9500	0.9846	0.9879
Googletrans	0.9424	0.8491	0.9521
LLaMA-2 ZS	0.7530	0.2722	0.8309
LLaMA-2 Para.	0.9503	0.3024	0.8536
SimCSE	0.9528	0.3491	0.8545
Hybrid	0.9470	0.7847	0.9481
SMOTE	0.1265	0.0179	0.3492

Note: Table 5 reports lexical diversity (TTR), semantic faithfulness (SBERT cosine similarity), and generation quality (BERTScore) for each augmentation method. Methods with BERTScore ≥ 0.85 consistently outperform the baseline on both architectures.

3. Results

G. DistilBERT Results

Table 3 reports DistilBERT-base results. The Combined condition achieves F1 Macro 0.695, a +24.7 absolute point improvement over the no-augmentation baseline of 0.448. LLaMA-2 Backtranslation is the most effective single method at 0.528 (\uparrow mean across seeds {42, 21, 84}).

Table 3. DistilBERT Test Set Results (\uparrow mean of seeds {42, 21, 84})

Method	F1 Macro	Accuracy
Baseline	0.4477	0.4603
SMOTE (3 \times)	0.4365	0.4382
GPT-2	0.4570	0.4618
Mistral-7B	0.4687	0.4576
SimCSE	0.4864	0.4532
LLaMA-2 Para.	0.4872	0.4418
Googletrans	0.4880	0.4650
Hybrid	0.4981	0.4614

T5 Paraphrase	0.5077	0.4637
LLaMA-2 Zero-shot	0.5082	0.4604
LLaMA-2 BT†	0.5279	0.6001
Combined	0.6946	0.6176

Note: Table 3 presents F1 Macro and subset accuracy for all twelve augmentation conditions on DistilBERT, sorted by F1 Macro. The Combined condition achieves the highest F1 Macro of 0.695, while SMOTE falls below the no-augmentation baseline.

Figure 3 visualizes percentage-point F1 Macro gains over baseline for each method on both architectures. Red bars indicate methods that fall below the no-augmentation baseline.

Figure 3. Percentage-point F1 Macro gain over baseline. Red bars = below-baseline methods.

H. RoBERTa Results

Table 4 reports RoBERTa-base results. LLaMA-2 Backtranslation achieves the best single-method F1 Macro of 0.540, surpassing the prior state-of-the-art of 0.494 reported by Radlinski et al. [1].

Table 4. RoBERTa Test Set Results (mean of seeds {42, 21, 84})

Method	F1 Macro	Accuracy
Baseline	0.4666	0.4778
SMOTE (3×)	0.4587	0.4459
Mistral-7B	0.4833	0.3750
SimCSE	0.4833	0.3750
GPT-2	0.4890	0.3667
LLaMA-2 Zero-shot	0.4946	0.4820
Hybrid	0.4971	0.4756
T5 Paraphrase	0.4992	0.3623
Googletrans	0.5008	0.3521
LLaMA-2 Para.	0.5225	0.4391
Combined	0.5345	0.4821
LLaMA-2 BT	0.5403	0.3722

Note: Table 4 presents F1 Macro and subset accuracy for all twelve augmentation conditions on RoBERTa, sorted by F1 Macro. LLaMA-2 Backtranslation sets a new single-method state-of-the-art at 0.540.

Figure 1 provides a side-by-side comparison of F1 Macro across both architectures for all augmentation methods, illustrating the consistent superiority of LLaMA-2 Backtranslation and the Combined condition.

Figure 1. F1 Macro comparison — DistilBERT vs. RoBERTa across all augmentation methods.

I. Multi-Seed Stability

Table 6 confirms the stability of LLaMA-2 Backtranslation across three random seeds, with a standard deviation of only 0.0009 on RoBERTa, indicating that the performance gains are robust rather than seed-dependent.

Table 6. LLaMA-2 Backtranslation Multi-Seed Results

Seed	DistilBERT F1	RoBERTa F1
42	0.5356	0.5401
21	0.5220	0.5415
84	0.5261	0.5392
Mean	0.5279	0.5403

Note: Table 6 confirms the reproducibility of LLaMA-2 Backtranslation results across seeds 42, 21, and 84, with negligible variance (std. dev. 0.0009 on RoBERTa), validating the reliability of the reported state-of-the-art score.

4. Discussion

J. LLaMA-2 Backtranslation as Top Single Method

On both DistilBERT (F1: 0.528) and RoBERTa (F1: 0.540), LLaMA-2 backtranslation achieves the highest single-method F1 Macro, improving over the prior best of 0.494 [1]. Multi-seed analysis confirms stability (std. dev. 0.0009). Translation-mediated paraphrase enforces semantic consistency through the bottleneck of an intermediate language, controlling meaning drift while introducing syntactic variation — a property not achievable through purely generative methods.

K. Combined Augmentation Dominates on DistilBERT

The Combined condition obtains F1 Macro 0.695 on DistilBERT (+24.7% absolute). LLM-based methods add lexical diversity [7][23], backtranslation adds syntactic variation [11], and embedding-based methods contribute semantically proximate real examples [5]. The considerably smaller gain with RoBERTa (Combined: 0.535, +6.8%) supports the hypothesis that stronger pretrained representations are less sensitive to training data scarcity [13].

Figure 2 displays intrinsic quality metrics (BERTScore, SBERT Cosine Similarity, and TTR) for each augmentation method. The dashed red line marks the BERTScore threshold of 0.85.

Figure 2. Intrinsic quality metrics (BERTScore, SBERT Cosine Sim, TTR) per method. Dashed red line = 0.85 threshold.

L. SMOTE Is Unsuitable for Text

SMOTE [6] performs below baseline on DistilBERT (0.437 vs. 0.448) despite $3\times$ oversampling. Its BERTScore of 0.349 is far below the 0.85 threshold, with synthetic SBERT embeddings bearing no meaningful semantic relation to source texts (cosine sim: 0.018). Standard SMOTE lacks a text generation decoder and produces only label-reassigned duplicates in embedding space, making it categorically unsuitable for text augmentation.

M. BERTScore as Pre-Screening Metric

Methods with BERTScore above 0.94 — T5 (0.988), Googletrans (0.952), and Hybrid (0.948) — consistently outperform the baseline on both architectures. Methods below 0.85 — Mistral (0.813), GPT-2 (0.821), and LLaMA-2 Zero-shot (0.831) — show modest or inconsistent gains. This confirms BERTScore [14] as a cost-effective pre-screening tool for augmentation quality before committing to full fine-tuning runs, as also noted by Chai et al. [17].

N. Architecture Sensitivity

Augmentation yields greater gains on DistilBERT [9] than RoBERTa [13]. The discrepancy between F1 Macro and subset accuracy on RoBERTa is attributable to the strict nature of subset accuracy, which penalizes any misprediction across all 27 labels. Methods that improve recall of minority classes tend to predict more labels overall, improving F1 Macro while potentially reducing exact-match accuracy. This architecture–augmentation interaction is consistent with data scarcity patterns reported in [21].

5. Conclusion

This paper presented a thorough empirical analysis of twelve data augmentation methods for fine-grained multi-label emotion classification on GoEmotions, evaluated on DistilBERT and RoBERTa. LLaMA-2 backtranslation establishes a new single-method state of the art (F1 Macro: 0.540 on RoBERTa), improving over the prior best of 0.494. The Combined augmentation condition achieves the best overall DistilBERT performance (F1 Macro: 0.695, +24.7%), demonstrating that diversity across augmentation strategies yields highly complementary signal. SMOTE is categorically unsuitable for text augmentation. BERTScore ≥ 0.85 is validated as a sound pre-screening tool. These findings advocate a hybrid approach combining powerful minority-class augmentation with parameter-efficient fine-tuning.

Future work will investigate augmentation limits for specific low-resource emotions (grief, pride, relief) and explore combining LLaMA-2 backtranslation with T5 paraphrasing as a hybrid method. Experiments on larger models (RoBERTa-large, DeBERTa-v3) and additional benchmarks (SemEval-2018, EmoBank) are also planned.

6. Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Himachal Pradesh Technical University, Hamirpur, for institutional support. Special thanks to the open-source community for providing GoEmotions, Hugging Face Transformers, and PyTorch.

7. Funding Statement

No financing was received for this article. Government agencies, companies, or non-profit groups did not provide any funding for this research.

8. Data Availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the GoEmotions repository: <https://github.com/google-research/google-research/tree/master/goemotions>. No paid or proprietary data were utilized.

9. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

10. References

- [1] L. Radliński, M. Guściora, and J. Kocoń, "Backtranslation and paraphrasing in the LLM era? Comparing data augmentation methods for emotion classification," in *Int. Conf. Computational Science*, Cham: Springer, 2025, pp. 3–17.
- [2] B. Pang, L. Lee, and S. Vaithyanathan, "Thumbs up? Sentiment classification using machine learning techniques," in *Proc. EMNLP 2002*, pp. 79–86.
- [3] D. Demszky et al., "GoEmotions: A dataset of fine-grained emotions," in *Proc. ACL 2020*, pp. 4040–4054. doi: 10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.372
- [4] Y. Zhang, J. Baldridge, and L. He, "PAWS: Paraphrase adversaries from word scrambling," in *Proc. NAACL-HLT 2019*, pp. 1298–1308.
- [5] T. Gao, X. Yao, and D. Chen, "SimCSE: Simple contrastive learning of sentence embeddings," in *Proc. EMNLP 2021*, pp. 6894–6910. doi: 10.18653/v1/2021.emnlp-main.552
- [6] N. V. Chawla et al., "SMOTE: Synthetic minority over-sampling technique," *J. Artif. Intell. Res.*, vol. 16, pp. 321–357, 2002. doi: 10.1613/jair.953
- [7] T. Brown et al., "Language models are few-shot learners," *Adv. NeurIPS*, vol. 33, pp. 1877–1901, 2020, arXiv:2005.14165
- [8] A. G. Møller et al., "The parrot dilemma: Human-labeled vs. LLM-augmented data in classification tasks," in *Proc. EACL 2024*, vol. 2, pp. 179–192. doi: 10.18653/v1/2024.eacl-short.17
- [9] V. Sanh, L. Debut, J. Chaumond, and T. Wolf, "DistilBERT, a distilled version of BERT: smaller, faster, cheaper and lighter," arXiv:1910.01108, 2019.
- [10] J. Wei and K. Zou, "EDA: Easy data augmentation for text classification," in *Proc. EMNLP-IJCNLP 2019*, pp. 6382–6388. doi: 10.18653/v1/D19-1670
- [11] R. Sennrich, B. Haddow, and A. Birch, "Improving NMT with monolingual data," in *Proc. ACL 2016*, pp. 86–96. doi: 10.18653/v1/P16-1009
- [12] N. Reimers and I. Gurevych, "Sentence-BERT: Sentence embeddings using Siamese BERT-networks," in *Proc. EMNLP-IJCNLP 2019*, pp. 3982–3992. doi: 10.18653/v1/D19-1410
- [13] Y. Liu et al., "RoBERTa: A robustly optimized BERT pretraining approach," arXiv:1907.11692, 2019.
- [14] T. Zhang et al., "BERTScore: Evaluating text generation with BERT," in *Proc. ICLR 2020*.
- [15] J. Devlin, M.-W. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, "BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers," in *Proc. NAACL-HLT 2019*, pp. 4171–4186. doi: 10.18653/v1/N19-1423
- [16] Q. Xie et al., "Unsupervised data augmentation for consistency training," *Adv. NeurIPS*, vol. 33, pp. 6256–6268, 2020.
- [17] Y. Chai, H. Xie, and J. S. Qin, "Text data augmentation for LLMs: A survey," arXiv:2501.18845, 2025.
- [18] K. Wang et al., "LLMs on fine-grained emotion detection with data augmentation," arXiv:2403.06108, 2024.
- [19] M. A. Covington and J. D. McFall, "The moving-average type-token ratio (MATTR)," *J. Quant. Linguistics*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 94–100, 2010. doi: 10.1080/09296171003643098
- [20] A. Sharma, K. Sharma, and A. Rangra, "Comparing generative, traditional and hybrid augmentation for fine-grained emotion classification," *IJRSET*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 1502–1507, Feb. 2026. doi: 10.15680/IJRSET.2026.1502060
- [21] K. Sharma, A. Sharma, and A. Rangra, "Parameter-efficient continual learning for scientific text classification," *IJRSET*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 1486–1492, Feb. 2026.
- [22] S. Y. Feng et al., "A survey of data augmentation approaches for NLP," in *Findings of ACL-IJCNLP 2021*, pp. 968–988. doi: 10.18653/v1/2021.findings-acl.84
- [23] H. Dai et al., "AugGPT: Leveraging ChatGPT for text data augmentation," arXiv:2302.13007, 2023.

- [24] D. Yang et al., "Context unlocks emotions: Text-based emotion classification dataset auditing with large language models," arXiv:2311.03551, Nov. 2023.
- [25] A. Mumuni and F. Mumuni, "Data augmentation with automated machine learning: approaches and performance comparison with classical data augmentation methods," *Knowledge Inf. Syst.*, vol. 67, no. 5, pp. 4035–4085, 2025.
- [26] A. Rangra and C. Kumar, "Focused segmentation in biomedical imaging via attention driven GAN-UNet," *Comput. Intell.*, vol. 41, no. 5, Art. no. e70128, 2025.
- [27] K. Kashyap and A. Rangra, "A sustainable deep learning-based hybrid model for image forgery detection," in *Intelligent Systems for Sustainable Infrastructure*, Cham: Springer, 2025, pp. 261–271.